

TECHNOLOGIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM-AS THE BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

B.U.Aminov

Qdpi (History Faculty Datsent)

S.Mirkhayitova

Qdpi (Senior Teacher)

Mamatkulova Gulnigorbonu

Chirchiq Master Of The Direction Of Management Of Educational
Institutions Of The Pedagogical Faculty Of The Dpu

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11654218>

Annotation: the article provides information on the impact of Science and technology on the material and spiritual life of mankind, as well as on the process of quality education.

Keywords: XX century, material and spiritual life, social necessity, educational system.

The 20th century took place from the history of the development of the human society as a period of revolutions that took place in the field of Science and technology. The high pace of development of Science and technology ensures that social relations acquire a new meaning, while enriching the process of material production theoretically (ideologically) and practically. The emergence of service industries, a new way of life laid the groundwork for the increase in the material and spiritual needs of people. The renewal and increase in social needs in turn necessitates the establishment of activities that ensure their short-term and quality satisfaction.

The field of Technology, a product of social necessity, and its improvement made it possible to produce a high-quality product at short intervals, with little physical effort. A tradition of a technological approach to the organization of the process of production of products has arisen in the fields of material production, processing of hom-ash (agriculture, industry, transport, domestic services, etc.). The technological approach serves to illuminate the general description of the production process. The process, which includes the period from the selection of raw materials for the purpose of producing a particular product (initial stage) to the delivery of the product to the consumer (final stage), is recognized as a technological process. The technological approach to the production process is manifested as an effective factor in achieving such goals as the organization of reforms in certain areas, ensuring their success, enriching the achievements achieved.

The implementation of modern, advanced, high-tech technologies in the areas of material production takes place under a number of conditions, in particular, reliance on the latest achievements of Science and Technology, large financial resources and the presence of qualified specialists with a high level of professional skills guarantee achievements in this regard.

It is also understood that the training of advanced technologies in the fields of material production is the achievement of a constant improvement in their professional skills, social, economic and cultural life develops on the principle of continuity, connection and integrity with each other. While the ideas and views that occupy a leading place in the social life of society have their influence on economic production and development, in turn, economic growth leads to an improvement in the cultural lifestyle of the population.

While in the lower stages of human civilization, activities aimed at educating a person, teaching him, are organized on the basis of simple, very simple requirements, to date

extremely strict and complex requirements are imposed on the organization of the educational process. CHunonchi, able to fully understand the essence of the production process, able to work with complex techniques, the social need to train a qualified specialist who is able to positively solve the problems that arise even in emergency situations presupposes the organization of the educational process on the basis of a technological approach.

Therefore, the scope of the tasks of pedagogical science, which is developing in an inextricable connection with social progress, is expanding.

At the same time, a stream of information is entering the social life of the Republic at a violent pace and is covering a wide range. One of the pressing problems facing the educational system is the rapid adoption of Information, its assessment, processing, theoretical generalization, conclusion and delivery to the student. The implementation of pedagogical technology in the educational process serves to positively solve the above-mentioned urgent problem.

The idea of technologizing the educational system was first thrown into the middle at the beginning of the last century in the era when a social movement arose to reform the educational system of Western Europe and the United States, to improve educational efficiency, to create certain conditions for the socialization of the individual. This idea was based on the introduction of the concept of "pedagogical technique" ("educational technique") into the educational process in the 30s. In the special literature created during these periods, the concept of "pedagogical (educational technique)" was interpreted in the manner of "sum of methods and tools that promote the clear and effective organization of training," and such situations as the introduction of educational and laboratory equipment into the educational process, their effective, productive use, explanation of the material content using visual weapons are the leading factors

In the 50s of the 20th century, the use of technical means in the educational process was recognized as a determining factor in the direction of "educational technology", the main focus was on issues such as expanding the audience of students, implementation at the cost of using technical means, further improving the capabilities of technical means, expanding their information capacity, qualitative Organization of The object of research in this regard, the possibilities of technical means as a focal point, the process of their improvement were adopted, and a special emphasis was placed on the study of the organizational aspects of the "technologization" of the educational process.

In the early 60s, the organization of the educational process on the basis of educational programming began to be seen as a factor revealing the essence of the concept of "technology". Software education implies that certain knowledge is given to students in a consistent, holistic way, and not as a separate part. For the first time, a proposal to organize the educational process according to a holistic, optimal program began to operate in the United States. Promoted by the "United Committee on software education and teaching machines". Software education in itself covers educational goals, criteria for changing and evaluating them in a suitable manner, as well as a clear description of the educational environment. This corresponds to the content of the concept of complete reorganization of the transformation complex. Quality education is associated with the fact that students are sufficiently educated. Therefore, the educational process in itself demonstrates the commonality of educational and educational tasks. One of the factors confirming the integrity

of educational and educational tasks of education is the manifestation of educational methods as some component of educational methods, and secondly, the methods of upbringing themselves are manifested as methods of stimulating education.

Education and upbringing promote the development of the individual. If students have a special developmental orientation and are involved in the mental development process, the educational development task will be effectively implemented.

The "educational process" is a broad concept and consists directly of such organizers as the educational process associated with any educational institution, education, upbringing, comprehensive development. In this process, the personal qualities of students are formed and developed. The main task of the educational process is considered to be the discovery of new scientific truths. Most types of knowledge are acquired by students not by direct viewing of the objects studied, but by perception through the teacher's story, description.

The use of complementary tools by students during the organization of the educational process raises them to a qualitatively new level. During this process, the issues facing the educational institution are carried out in a complex. During the consideration of the structural structure of the educational process, it is necessary to determine its main components of the structure and the connections between them. Education is considered one of the types of personality activity. It necessarily refers to the interactions between the teacher and the one being taught, which take place under certain set conditions.

The educational process consists of two interconnected processes – teaching and learning. Education is not organized without the simultaneous activities of the teacher and those being taught, without their mutual didactic dependence. No matter how active the teacher is in communicating knowledge, if the students themselves do not take a conscious approach to mastering knowledge, then the educational process will not come true. Therefore, in the process of education, it is not the mere influence of the educator on the student that should be ensured, but their solidarity.

At the same time, the educational process is not considered a mechanical sum of teaching and learning processes. This is a qualitatively new, whole phenomenon, the content of which is reflected by didactic interactions in different forms. In one whole, integrity of this process, the totality of teaching and learning goals will be hidden, the impossibility of teaching without such learning. Education means not only a process of a cognitive nature, but also the interaction of the teacher and students. One type of information affects the inner world of students in different ways. Communication in the educational process has a very strong influence on the interpretation of the need for learning. The formation of a positive attitude towards reading serves to create favorable moral and psychological conditions for active learning.

The positive attitude of the teacher to his subject in the educational process has a very strong influence on the process of effective assimilation of knowledge, the ability to extend a helping hand to students in time, timely and truthful assessment of their achievements, successes, self-control in difficult situations. In students, choosing a teacher as an ideal for themselves, consistent reading and learning of knowledge ensures that they are formed as specialists. Quality education is associated with the fact that students are sufficiently educated. Therefore, the educational process in itself demonstrates the commonality of educational and educational tasks. One of the factors confirming the integrity of educational and educational tasks of education is the manifestation of educational methods as some component of

educational methods, and secondly, the methods of upbringing themselves are manifested as methods of stimulating education.

Education and upbringing promote the development of the individual. If students have a special developmental orientation and are involved in the mental development process, the educational development task will be effectively implemented.

The "educational process" is a broad concept and consists directly of such organizers as the educational process associated with any educational institution, education, upbringing, comprehensive development. In this process, the personal qualities of students are formed and developed. The main task of the educational process is considered to be the discovery of new scientific truths. Most types of knowledge are acquired by students not by direct viewing of the objects studied, but by perception through the teacher's story, description.

The use of complementary tools by students during the organization of the educational process raises them to a qualitatively new level. During this process, the issues facing the educational institution are carried out in a complex. During the consideration of the structural structure of the educational process, it is necessary to determine its main components of the structure and the connections between them. Education is considered one of the types of personality activity. It necessarily refers to the interactions between the teacher and the one being taught, which take place under certain set conditions.

The educational process consists of two interconnected processes – teaching and learning. Education is not organized without the simultaneous activities of the teacher and those being taught, without their mutual didactic dependence. No matter how active the teacher is in communicating knowledge, if the students themselves do not take a conscious approach to mastering knowledge, then the educational process will not come true. Therefore, in the process of education, it is not the mere influence of the educator on the student that should be ensured, but their solidarity.

At the same time, the educational process is not considered a mechanical sum of teaching and learning processes. This is a qualitatively new, whole phenomenon, the content of which is reflected by didactic interactions in different forms. In one whole, integrity of this process, the totality of teaching and learning goals will be hidden, the impossibility of teaching without such learning. Education means not only a process of a cognitive nature, but also the interaction of the teacher and students. One type of information affects the inner world of students in different ways. Communication in the educational process has a very strong influence on the interpretation of the need for learning. The formation of a positive attitude towards reading serves to create favorable moral and psychological conditions for active learning. The positive attitude of the teacher to his subject in the educational process has a very strong influence on the process of effective assimilation of knowledge, the ability to extend a helping hand to students in time, timely and truthful assessment of their achievements, successes, self-control in difficult situations. In students, choosing a teacher as an ideal for themselves, consistent reading and learning of knowledge ensures that they are formed as specialists.

References:

1. SH.M. Mirziyoyev is the patron saint of the Republic of Uzbekistan in a solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of

Uzbekistan on the topic" the provision of the rule of Law and human interests – the Pledge of the progressives of the land and the welfare of the people". - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.

2. SH.M. Mirziyoyev critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility-should be the Daily rule of the activities of each leader. - T.: Uzbekistan. – 2017.

3. SH.M. Mirziyoyev critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility-should be the Daily rule of the activities of each leader. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.

4. SH.M. Mirziyoyev will build our great future together with our brave and Noble ring. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.

5. SH.M. Mirziyoyev" constitution-a solid foundation for our free and prosperous life, for the further development of our country " is the product of a solemn ceremony dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

